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Increasing Trend of Undernutrition with age among under 5 children: A Community Based Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Undernutrition remains a major public health issue among under-five children in India, particularly in rural areas. This study aimed to assess the age-wise distribution and patterns of undernutrition. **Methods:** A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 374 under-five children in rural Varanasi. Anthropometric measurements were used to classify undernutrition as underweight, stunting, and wasting according to WHO criteria. Socio-demographic data were also collected and analysed. **Results:** The overall prevalence of undernutrition was 48.4%. Stunting (39.6%) was the most common form, followed by underweight (36.1%) and wasting (21.3%). An increasing trend of stunting and underweight was observed with age, while wasting was more prevalent in younger children, especially those aged 13–36 months. Undernutrition was more common among children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds and larger families. **Conclusion:** The findings reveal a high burden of undernutrition, with a clear age-related increase in chronic forms. Early and sustained nutritional interventions are essential, particularly during and beyond the weaning period, to reduce the long-term impact of malnutrition.

Keywords: Undernutrition, Stunting, Wasting, Underweight, Rural Varanasi, Under-Five, Nutritional Surveillance.

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Introduction

India contributes a third of the global burden of undernutrition¹. Undernutrition is associated with high rates of mortality and morbidity and is an underlying factor in almost one-third to half of all children under five years who die each year of preventable causes. Strong evidence exists on the synergism between undernutrition and child mortality due to common childhood illnesses including diarrhoea, acute respiratory infections, malaria, and measles. In addition to increasing the risk of mortality, undernutrition leads to growth retardation and impaired psychosocial and cognitive development, which further impacts educational attainment².

Undernutrition encompasses three major indicators: wasting (low weight-for-height), stunting (low height-for-age), and underweight (low weight-for-age)¹. According to the Joint Malnutrition Estimates (JME) 2024, stunting affected an estimated 22.3% or 148.1 million child under five globally in 2022. Wasting threatened the lives of approximately 6.8% or 45 million children, and overweight was observed in 5.6% or 37 million children in the same age group³. As per the National Family Health

Survey (NFHS-5, 2019–2021), the national prevalence among under-five children in India was 35.5% for stunting, 19.3% for wasting, 7.7% for severe wasting, 32.1% for underweight, and 3.4% for overweight⁴.

Monitoring trends in child malnutrition is essential to assess progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Target 2.2, which aims to “end all forms of malnutrition by 2030.” This target is embedded within SDG 2 to “end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture”⁵.

A study by Martorell and Young (2012), using nationally representative data from India and Guatemala, highlighted that undernutrition in children under five manifests differently across age groups. In India, wasting was most prevalent in infants aged 0–5 months (30%) and declined with age, whereas stunting increased steadily, peaking at 58% in children aged 18–23 months. The study emphasized the significance of maternal factors such as low BMI and short stature, along with household poverty, in contributing to both stunting and wasting. These findings underline the multifactorial nature of undernutrition and the importance of age-specific analyses⁶.

Despite the implementation of several national programs aimed at improving child nutrition, undernutrition remains a pressing public health concern in India, especially in rural areas. While extensive research exists on the overall burden of malnutrition, limited attention has been given to how undernutrition trends vary with age among under-five children. Understanding this distribution is crucial for the development of targeted and age-appropriate interventions.

Therefore, this community-based cross-sectional study was undertaken to assess the prevalence of undernutrition specifically stunting, wasting, and underweight among children under five years of age, and to explore how the burden of undernutrition changes with increasing age in this population.

Methodology

A community-based cross-sectional study was undertaken to assess the prevalence of undernutrition and to examine its age-wise distribution among under-five children in rural areas of Varanasi. The study was conducted over a two-year period, from October 2023 - March 2024. The study population comprised children aged 0-59 months residing in the selected rural regions. The sample size for this study was determined by the prevalence of underweight in under-five children (45%) reported by *Prem Shankar Mishra et al (2021)*⁷, was used along with a 95% confidence level and an allowable margin of error of 7.5%. After adjusting for a design effect of 2 to account for the sampling method and incorporating an anticipated 10% non-response rate, the final required sample size was calculated to be 374 under-five children.

Children were included if they were under five years of age and their parents or legal guardians provided informed consent. Exclusion criteria included children who were acutely ill at the time of data collection or whose guardian declined participation. Multi -Stage sampling method was used to get required sample population. Out of 8 Community Development Block in rural area of Varanasi, Chiraigaon Block was selected randomly. The villages of Chiraigaon Block divided into three strata according to the total population. Two villages will be selected from each of these three strata randomly. Probability Proportion to Size Sampling (PPSS) was adopted to get the required number of under 5 children from the selected villages. A house-to-house survey method was employed for data collection. On average, five to seven households were visited per day, with a similar number of children examined daily. In each selected household, the youngest eligible child under five years of age was enrolled. If no eligible child was present, the adjacent household to the right was approached until a suitable participant was identified.

Prior to data collection, the objectives and procedures of the study were explained to the parents or guardians, and written informed consent was obtained. Data were collected using a structured and pre-tested questionnaire, which was divided into three sections. The first section gathered socio-demographic data, including child's age and sex, parental education and occupation, family size, birth order, birth interval, and breastfeeding practices. Udai Pareek Scale was used for measuring socio - economic status⁸. The second section focused on environmental characteristics such as type of housing, ventilation status, overcrowding, and access to basic amenities. The third section encompassed nutritional assessment, incorporating anthropometric measurements of the children's weight and height.

The weight measurement of the children less than one year of age was measured using Infant weighing scale and the weight of the children more than one year of age was measured using Digital Bathroom weighing scale. The children were in minimal clothing and without footwear when measurements were taken. Length Measurement for children less than 2 years measured using Infantometer. Height measurement for children more than 2 years measured using Stadiometer. Mid Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) measured using Shakir Tape used for measurement.

Operational Definitions 9:

- **Stunting:** Height - For - Age \leq 2 SD of the WHO Child growth standards.
- **Wasting:** Weight - For -Height \leq 2 SD of the WHO Child growth standards.
- **Underweight:** Weight-For-Age \leq 2 SD of the WHO Child growth standards.

Under 5 Children having **at least any one** of the following considered as undernourished children in this study.

1. Underweight
2. Stunting
3. Wasting

Data Analysis: Data were initially entered into Microsoft Excel and subsequently analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25.0 (Trial Edition; IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the data, with results presented as frequencies and percentages, as appropriate. The Chi-square test was used to examine associations between the nutritional status of under-five children and selected risk factors. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, with reference number Dean/2023/EC/6602, dated on 09.10.2023

Results

The findings of the study provide insights into the nutritional status of under-five children in the community and explore the association of undernutrition with age and other background variables. The analysis highlights both the overall burden and age-wise patterns of nutritional deficiencies among children.

Out of the total 374 under-five children included in the study, 48.4% (181) were found to be undernourished, while 51.6% (193) had a normal nutritional status (Figure 1). This indicates that nearly half of the children were suffering from some form of undernutrition, emphasizing a significant public health concern. Among the different forms of undernutrition observed in the study population, stunting was the most prevalent, affecting 39.6% (n=148) of the children. This was followed by underweight in 36.1% (n = 135) and wasting in 21.3% (n = 80) of the children (**Table 1**).

Table- 1: Prevalence of Different Types of Undernutrition

Different types of Undernutrition	No.	%
Underweight	135	36.1
Stunting	148	39.6
Wasting	80	21.3

Figure-1: Nutritional status of under-5 children

The analysis of socio-demographic variables in relation to nutritional status among under-five children revealed notable patterns. Undernutrition was most prevalent in the 49-60 months age group, where nearly two-thirds (66.7%) of children were undernourished. In contrast, the lowest prevalence was observed in the 13-24 months age group (36.8%). These findings suggest a rising trend of undernutrition with increasing age, highlighting the growing vulnerability of older preschool-aged children. Gender-wise distribution showed a marginal difference, with slightly higher undernutrition among male children (50.4%) compared to females (45.3%) (**Table -2**).

Table-2: Association of Socio-Demographic variables with Nutritional Status of under-five children (N = 374)

Socio - Demographic Variables		Normal (n = 193)		Undernutrition (n = 181)		P value
		No.	%	No.	%	
Age Groups (in months)	0 – 12	30	46.2	35	53.8	0.04*
	13 – 24	48	63.2	28	36.8	
	25 – 36	50	51.0	48	49.0	
	37 – 48	45	60.0	30	40.0	
	49 – 60	20	33.3	40	66.7	
Gender	Male	111	49.6	113	50.4	0.238
	Female	82	54.7	68	45.3	
Religion	Hindu	184	51.1	176	48.9	0.333
	Muslim	9	64.3	5	35.7	
Caste	SC&ST	67	51.9	62	48.1	0.577
	OBC	116	50.9	112	49.1	
	Others	10	58.8	7	41.2	
Size of the family	< 5 Members	123	52.3	112	47.7	0.249
	≥ 5 Members	70	50.4	69	49.6	
Education of the Head of the Family	Illiterate	44	55.0	36	45.0	0.495
	Primary School	27	56.3	21	43.8	
	Middle School	23	54.8	19	45.2	
	High School	38	48.7	40	51.3	
	Intermediate	35	50.7	34	49.3	
	Graduate	24	47.1	27	52.9	
	Post Graduate	2	33.3	4	66.7	
Occupation of the Head of Family	Unemployed	41	58.6	29	41.4	0.516
	Unskilled	83	46.6	95	53.4	
	Semi - Skilled	43	57.3	32	42.7	
	Skilled	7	77.8	2	22.2	
	Clerical	2	66.7	1	33.3	
	Semi - Professional	11	45.8	13	54.2	
	Professional	6	40.0	9	60.0	
Socio Economic Status (SES)	Upper Class	30	60.0	20	40.0	0.125
	Upper Middle Class	20	71.4	8	28.6	
	Middle Class	33	50.0	33	50.0	
	Lower Middle Class	83	49.4	85	50.6	
	Lower Class	27	43.5	35	56.5	

Children from Hindu families had similar rates of undernutrition (48.9%) compared to those from Muslim households (35.7%), indicating limited variation by religion. Caste-based differences were also minimal, with undernutrition rates ranging between 41.2% and 49.1% across SC/ST, OBC, and other caste categories. Family size appeared to have little impact on nutritional outcomes, as undernutrition was reported among 47.7% of children from families with fewer than five members and 49.6% among those from larger families (Table 2).

Parental education, particularly which of the head of the household, did not show a consistent relationship with undernutrition. While households headed by illiterate individuals had a higher proportion of undernourished children (45.0%), those led by individuals with postgraduate education surprisingly had an even higher rate (66.7%).

This lack of a linear pattern may reflect the influence of multiple overlapping factors beyond education alone. In terms of occupation, the highest burden of undernutrition was observed among children from professional families (60.0%) and those whose heads of household were semi-professionals (54.2%) or unskilled workers (53.4%) (Table-2).

Figure-2: Trend of undernutrition with age among under- 5 children

Socio-economic status, as measured by the Udai Pareek scale, showed that undernutrition was most prominent in lower (56.5%) and lower middle (50.6%) classes. However, a significant proportion of undernourished children was also noted in higher socioeconomic strata, such as upper-middle (28.6%) and upper class (40.0%) families, indicating that undernutrition is not exclusively a problem of the poor.

The table 3 presents the age-stratified distribution of undernutrition among under-five children, with specific focus on underweight, stunting, and wasting. The prevalence of underweight increased progressively with age, from 18.5% in the 0-12 month’s group to 48.3% among children aged 49-60 months. Similarly, stunting was highest in the 49-60 months group (65.0%), with a significant initial burden also observed in infants aged 0-12 months (47.7%). In contrast, wasting, an indicator of acute malnutrition was most prominent during the 13-24 months (28.9%) and 25-36 months (27.6%) age groups. Wasting declined with age, reaching its lowest level in the 49-60 months group (11.7%)

Table-3: Trend of underweight, stunting, and wasting across age groups 0–59 months

Age groups	Underweight		Stunting		Wasting	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
13-24 months	21	27.6	19	25.0	22	28.9
25-36 months	44	44.9	33	33.7	27	27.6
37-48 months	29	38.7	26	34.7	10	13.3
49-60 months	29	48.3	39	65.0	7	11.7
Total	135	36.1	148	39.6	80	21.3

Discussion

Childhood malnutrition remains a critical public health issue in many developing countries, including India. The present study underscores this concern, reporting an overall undernutrition prevalence of 48.4% among under-five children in rural Varanasi. Among the types of malnutrition observed, stunting was most prevalent (39.6%), followed by underweight (36.1%), wasting (15.2%), and severe wasting (6.1%), indicating the presence of both chronic and acute forms of nutritional deficiency in the study population.

Overall, the data reveal a progressive increase in chronic forms of undernutrition (underweight and stunting) with advancing age, while acute undernutrition (wasting) is more prominent in younger age groups. This age-wise distribution is also effectively illustrated in (Figure-2), which visually underscores the disproportionate burden of stunting and underweight in older under-five children, reinforcing the need for age-specific nutritional strategies.

These findings are broadly comparable to national estimates reported in NFHS-5 (2019 - 21), which documented stunting at 35.5%, underweight at 32.1%, wasting at 19.3%, and severe wasting at 7.7%. However, the slightly elevated rates of stunting and underweight in this cohort may reflect specific regional disparities in health and nutrition⁴.

NFHS-5 report of Varanasi district indicates a decline in stunting from 38.4% to 35.5%, present study observed a stunting rate of 39.6%, exceeding the district average. Similarly, the prevalence of underweight in this sample (36.1%) was higher than the NFHS-5 estimate of 32.1%, and wasting was also more prevalent (21.3%) compared to the NFHS-5 figure of 19.3%. These discrepancies suggest that, despite district-wide improvements reflected in NFHS-5, rural pockets such as Chiragaon Block continue to experience a disproportionately high burden of undernutrition. This divergence may be attributed to several factors, including socio-economic deprivation, limited access to quality health and nutrition services, poor maternal literacy, and suboptimal infant and young child feeding practices. Furthermore, the NFHS data are aggregate estimates that include both urban and rural populations, whereas present study is specifically focused on a rural setting, which is often more vulnerable due to infrastructural and service delivery gaps. These findings highlight the persistent rural-urban divide in child health outcomes and reinforce the need for targeted, decentralized interventions aimed at high-risk areas within districts⁴.

Previous studies from various regions of India have shown considerable variation, with underweight prevalence ranging from 39% to 75%, stunting from 15.4% to 74%, and wasting from 10.6% to 42.3%¹⁰⁻¹⁵. These wide disparities are likely influenced by diverse socio-demographic and environmental factors, such as poverty, maternal illiteracy, suboptimal infant feeding practices, food insecurity, and poor hygiene and sanitation. In rural areas like Varanasi, such factors may interact synergistically to heighten the risk of malnutrition, particularly in vulnerable age groups

Several studies across India and other low- and middle-income countries have documented socio-demographic determinants of undernutrition, reinforcing the patterns observed in the current study. The higher prevalence of undernutrition among older preschool children (particularly those aged 49 - 60 months) aligns with previous reports indicating that nutritional vulnerability tends to increase with age due to weaning challenges, inadequate dietary diversification, and decreasing parental attention as children grow older^{16, 17}. In the present study, a marginally higher prevalence of undernutrition was observed among male children (50.4%) compared to females (45.3%), though this difference was not statistically significant. This finding contrasts with several studies from different parts of India which have reported a higher burden of undernutrition among girls, suggesting the presence of gender-based discrimination in nutritional care, particularly in resource-limited rural households^{18,19}.

Religion and caste did not demonstrate marked disparities in nutritional outcomes in this study. These findings are consistent with other community-based studies in India, which have found that the influence of religion or caste on child malnutrition tends to diminish when adjusted for socioeconomic and environmental variables^{20,21}. Occupational class also failed to show a clear gradient, though undernutrition was notably higher among unskilled and semi-professional groups, a trend mirrored in studies from Bihar and West Bengal²².

Socioeconomic status remains a well-established risk factor for undernutrition²³. Our findings of higher undernutrition in the lower and lower middle socioeconomic classes. This phenomenon may be explained by poor maternal education, cultural food taboos, or lack of awareness about child nutrition, which have been reported in studies from both urban and rural India^{24,25}.

The age-specific distribution of undernutrition observed in the present study provides crucial insights into the evolving vulnerability of under-five children. A clear upward trend in both underweight and stunting was evident with increasing age, peaking at 48.3% and 65.0%, respectively, in the 49–60 months age group. Stunting, as a manifestation of chronic undernutrition, is well-recognized for its long-term implications on cognitive development, physical health, and adult human capital^{26,27}. These findings align with prior studies emphasizing the importance of targeted nutritional interventions during early life, particularly within the first 1,000 days²⁸.

In contrast, the pattern of wasting a marker of acute malnutrition peaked in the 13- 36 months age groups and declined thereafter. This age group corresponds to the critical transition from exclusive breastfeeding to complementary feeding, a period often characterized by inadequate nutrient intake, increased risk of infections, and exposure to environmental pathogens^{29,30}. Collectively, these findings emphasize the need for comprehensive, age-sensitive nutritional and health strategies that address both acute and chronic forms of undernutrition in early childhood.

Prospective Cohort study done at Puducherry where a lower baseline prevalence of undernutrition (15.8%) was reported, with underweight at (9.6%), wasting at (7.7%), and stunting at (7.3%). Importantly, over a one-year follow-up period that involved regular growth monitoring, counselling of mothers, and community engagement, they documented a significant decline in wasting by 63.6%, underweight by 44.8%, and stunting by 31.5%. These results highlight the effectiveness of continuous monitoring and targeted interventions in reversing early undernutrition trends, particularly acute malnutrition.

This study, while offering valuable insights into the age-specific burden of undernutrition among under-five children in rural Varanasi, but being cross - sectional design restricts causal inference. The study did not assess micronutrient deficiencies, dietary intake patterns, or maternal nutritional status, which are important determinants of child undernutrition. Inclusion of these parameters in future longitudinal studies may provide a more comprehensive understanding of malnutrition dynamics in early childhood.

Conclusion

This study highlights a substantial burden of undernutrition among under-five children in rural Varanasi, with a notable age-related increase in the prevalence of underweight and stunting. While wasting was more prominent in early infancy and toddler hood, chronic forms of malnutrition intensified with age, particularly after 36 months. These findings underscore the need for sustained, age-specific nutritional interventions that address both acute and chronic undernutrition. Strengthening community-based programs like ICDS and *Poshan Abhiyaan*, ensuring effective complementary feeding practices, empowering caregivers through nutrition education, and routine growth monitoring at the grassroots level are critical.

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